

**THE MUSAVAT UNDERGROUND IN THE FIGHT FOR THE
RESTORATION OF THE STATE INDEPENDENCE OF AZERBAIJAN
(1920-1926)**

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<i>Citation</i>	Alizade, A. (2021). THE MUSAVAT UNDERGROUND IN THE FIGHT FOR THE RESTORATION OF THE STATE INDEPENDENCE OF AZERBAIJAN (1920-1926). <i>Istanbul Aydın University Journal of Social Sciences</i> , 13(3), 663 - 678.
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ABSTRACT

This article explores the history of the struggle of the Musavat underground for the restoration of the state independence of Azerbaijan in 1920–1926. It describes methods of struggle, the structure of underground organizations, educational activity and the links of the underground with foreign partners and emigration. The study was carried out mainly on the basis of investigative cases of arrested members of the underground. In addition, other sources were also used in the work. In connection with the consistent presentation of events, the article used the narrative method of study. The scientific novelty of the work is that this study is being conducted for the first time. The main conclusion is that the Musavat underground laid the foundation for the struggle of the Azerbaijani people for the restoration of state independence immediately after the occupation of the country by the troops of Bolshevik Russia and played an exceptional role in the growth of national self-awareness.

Keywords: *Musavat, Secret Organization, Anti-Sovietism, Anti-bolshevism, Independence of Azerbaijan, Repression.*

INTRODUCTION

The clandestine activity of Musavatists for the restoration of the state independence of Azerbaijan began immediately after the occupation of Azerbaijan by the troops of Bolshevik Russia on April 28, 1920. The inability of the Azerbaijani authorities to prevent the occupation of the country led to a split in the country's former ruling party, Musavat, which revived its activities in a new capacity and in a reformed form from the moment of occupation. From that time, it actually became a leftist Turkic nationalist party. The Musavatists were the only organized force in Azerbaijan capable of putting up serious resistance to the invaders and local Bolsheviks, and that's why the entire repressive machine of the Bolshevik regime was directed against them from the very first days of the occupation.

The only detailed document shedding light on the activities of the Azerbaijani underground is the investigative "Case of Dadash Hasanov and Others" (Archival Number 500518) in seven volumes compiled by the staff of the Azerbaijan State Political Department, which is kept in the archive of the State Security Service of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main account of the events in this study is based on this source. In addition, the article also uses other sources and studies of scientists.

I. THE MUSAVAT UNDERGROUND IN 1920-1923

Formation of the underground

Immediately after the occupation of the country, the Bolsheviks began to exert pressure on all political parties of the country with a view to securing the recognition of the legitimacy of the occupying regime [[M. B. Mammedzade 1992, p. 147](#)]. As a result, many parties either disbanded or merged with the Azerbaijan Communist Party (Bolsheviks).

As for the ruling Musavat party, according to a member of the first underground Central Committee (CC), Mammad Sadikh Guliyev, its members announced "a struggle against bureaucracy and bourgeois elements that penetrated the party" [[Final Decree 1926, p. 2](#)]. The new initiative group of the leftist Musavat included 25 people, including Mirzabala Mammadov (Mammadzadeh), Abdul Vahhab Mammadzadeh (Yurtsever), Mammad-Sadikh Guliyev, Rasim Gasimov, Seyid Zargar and others. The chairman of the Central Committee of the first underground was Mirzabala Mammadzadeh (Mammadov). The ideological leader of the Azerbaijani resistance was Mammad Amin Rasulzadeh, the former chairman of the Azerbaijani National Council, which declared the independence of

On April 29, 1920, the Musavat Party held an extraordinary congress where several members of this party proposed dissolving the party and joining the Bolsheviks.

However, this initiative was rejected by the majority, which insisted on the independence of Azerbaijan, the struggle against the occupying forces and their withdrawal from the country [[Mammedzade 1992, p. 148-149](#)]. Students of Baku University were especially active at the congress.

The congress elected the new Central Committee of the Musavat Party, consisting of 15 people, which included the initiative group mentioned above. The Central Committee adopted an appeal to the Bolsheviks, demanding legal activity within the framework of the law, but this demand was rejected. Azerbaijan in 1918.

Illustration 1. Case of Dadash Hasanov and others No: 500518 Archive of State Security of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Source: Archive of State Security of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Work on the organized resistance of the underground to the occupation was carried out during 1920-1922. The Musavatists were sure that, in view of the difficult international situation, the occupation would not last long and therefore began to create not only a new party, but also paramilitary units. The activities were conducted in two directions: propaganda of the idea of restoring Azerbaijan's state independence and preparing an armed uprising against the occupiers.

The meetings of the members of the leadership of the first clandestine organization were most often conducted in the house of Dadash Hasanov (Hasanzadeh), one of the most active members of the underground and a doctor of the therapeutic clinic of Azerbaijan State University. These meetings criticized the Musavat emigration,

specifically, Mirzabala Mammadzadeh accused them of inaction. According to him, it is impossible to expect any specific actions against the invaders from the emigrants, and therefore we ourselves must organize the struggle against the Bolsheviks [[Final Decree 1926, p. 7](#)].

The organ of the clandestine organization of Musavat was the newspaper Istiqlal (Independence), which began to be published from 1922. In total, 18 editions of the newspaper with 30-50 copies were published. The party's program and leaflets were also printed, which contained calls for the restoration of Azerbaijan's state independence.

Organizational structure of the underground

By 1921, Musavat had the following organizational structure, which operated until the defeat of the first underground by the Azerbaijan State Political Department in 1923:

1. The Central Committee, which included the party's top leadership. The chairman of the Central Committee was Mirzabala Mammadzadeh (1898-1959);
2. Baku Committee (BC) headed by Abdul Vahhab Mammadzadeh.
3. Military organization;
4. Party cells in Baku and the counties of Azerbaijan. Four district organizations operated in Baku, each of which was headed by three people. In the counties, organizations were established in Salyan and Lankaran, but the cell in Ganja was especially influential. There were plans to create party cells in Dagestan and Turkestan, but it was impossible to implement them.

Structure and objectives of the military organization

The military organization, whose general leader was Dadash Hasanov [[Yurtsever 1954, p. 18](#)] until 1923, was of particular importance in the structure of the Musavat underground. The fact is that it was precisely through an armed insurrection that it was planned to put an end to the occupying regime.

From the beginning of 1923, the military organization under the Central Committee was headed by five members including Mammad Sadikh Guliyev, Ahmad Hajinski, Ibrahim Akhundzadeh, Ali Huseyn Dadashov and Isfandiyar Vakilov. Meetings of the five under the Central Committee were held in Dadashov's apartment.

At the same time, there was also a military organization under the BC led by five people including Nurulla Gulibayov (campaigning), Ibrahim Akhundzadeh (organizational issues), Nurulla Rzabayov (supply), Movsum Ibrahimov (communication) and Ibrahim Atakishiyev (working with military groups). Movsum Baydamirov and Nasrullah Rizabayli were also active members of the

military organization. D. Hasanov and A. Hajinski also took part in the work of the military organization under the BC. The meetings of the BC military department were held mainly at the apartment of Dr. Dadash Hasanov, who organized troikas of activists in the counties for propaganda among the military.

The military organization had the following departments:

1. Organizational department engaged in the recruitment of new members;
2. Operational department in charge of collecting intelligence data on Red Army units;
3. Supply department responsible for providing weapons and ammunition to participants in the planned insurrection.
4. Propaganda department engaged in promoting the ideas of the independence of Azerbaijan, the need for armed action against the occupiers and for the seizure of strategic facilities, as well as winning over Red Army soldiers and officers.

The leaders of the military organization divided Baku into sectors, each of which had its own cell with a leader who was supposed to mobilize all the available people on the day of the uprising.

The date of the beginning of the uprising was not indicated, and it was required to expect a command from the Central Committee of Musavat at any time. In any case, it was planned to start it directly after the uprising in Georgia. Movsum Ibrahimov, the chief of the economic team of the staff of the People's Commissariat for Military and Navy Affairs, promised to provide weapons to the insurgents.

Thanks to active propaganda in the Red Army, the Musavatists succeeded in winning over a considerable number of officers. The investigative case mentions Ishag Dadashov, the chief of the machine-gun team of the Azerbaijani Combined Military School, Zakariya Vakilov, the chief of the engineering squad, Soyun Pashayev, assistant to the battery commander, and Warrant Officer Suleyman Hajiyev, assistant to the commander of the staff of the People's Commissariat for Military and Navy Affairs. The uprising was to be supported by about 80 cadets of the Azerbaijani Combined Military School.

According to the investigative case, by 1923 the military organization of Musavat had cells in the Azerbaijani Combined Military School, Aviation School, the convoy team of the Azerbaijan SSR and the 3rd regiment of the Azerbaijani division in Ganja.

The military organization even had access to classified information, thanks to the file clerk of the Staff of the People's Commissariat for Military and Navy Affairs, Seyid Mir Bagir Rzayev, which he handed over to Dadash Hasanov and Ahmad Hajinski.

Relations with Turkish representatives

The Central Committee of the Musavat Party in the underground in 1920-1921 had secret connections with the Turkish consulate in Baku, specifically, Consul Memduh Sevket Bey. However, the Turks did not render any tangible support to the Musavatists. The help was limited only to communication services and some amount of money.

According to the investigation, the Turks helped organize the escape of the former chairman of the National Council of Azerbaijan, Mammad Amin Rasulzadeh, from Moscow to Istanbul. This secret operation of the Musavat underground was carried out in 1922 by Dadash Hasanov, Rahim Vakilov and the famous Tatar enlightener Musa Bigiyev [[Yurtsever 1954, p.18](#)].

Of great interest is the correspondence between Mirzabala Mammadzadeh and a Turk named Edin, who performed some secret mission during the uprising in Ajaria in 1922 [[Final Decree 1926, p. 22-23](#)]. Mammadzadeh explained to him his views on the expected incorporation of Azerbaijan into the USSR. According to him, there will be no union of republics. They just want to incorporate Azerbaijan into Russia and consolidate the occupation legally.

He further mentioned that starting from December 2, in protest against the entry into the USSR, an uprising began in Karabakh and Shamakhi. The Shollar water pipeline, which supplied water to Baku, was destroyed, while activists of the Communist Party were killed in several counties; the Caucasus and Mercury shipyard, which sent steamships loaded with Baku oil to Russia, was burnt. The suburbs of Baku were also uneasy: oil fields were burned and the supply of oil to Russia was disrupted. The uprising was suppressed by the army and about 200 people were arrested. At the end of his letter, Mammadzadeh wrote that their resources were limited and if the Turks did not help, the uprising would be finally suppressed. However, in response to this request, Edin did not promise anything concrete, except for moral support and some amount of money.

Cooperation with the Joint Committee of Georgia

Great importance in the activity of the Musavat underground was attached to links with the Georgian anti-Soviet movement [[Mamulia](#)]. They had common goals for restoring the state independence of both countries. In addition, the Musavatists hoped for help from the Entente through contacts with the Georgian Mensheviks.

After the occupation of Georgia by the troops of Bolshevik Russia, all major parties of the country decided to overcome internal contradictions and join forces against the occupation. This led to the creation of the "Committee for the Independence of Georgia" (Joint Committee).

In 1921, Mirzabala Mamedzadeh visited Tiflis three times and met with one of the leaders of the Georgian underground Sylvester Djibladze. The Georgian partners insisted on the establishment of the same committee in Azerbaijan and other regions of the Caucasus. After that, it was planned to create a united Caucasian center for these committees with the aim of preparing and leading an uprising against the occupying forces.

After the talks, Mammadzadeh began to attempt to create the Joint Committee of Azerbaijan, and the Musavatists began to maintain permanent ties with Tiflis. Initially, this work was entrusted to Aliofsat Najafov. But after his arrest in 1923, this mission was temporarily performed by Dadash Hasanov. Mirzabala Mammadzadeh sent him to Tiflis, where he met with the former minister of the Menshevik government of Georgia, Noah Khomeriki, who returned from exile to organize an uprising against the Bolsheviks. [Concluding Resolution 1926, p. 31]. After this, a connection was established with the representative of the Georgian Mensheviks in Baku, G. Salukvadze. After Hasanov, work in this direction was continued by Ali Yusifzadeh, who was arrested by the Azerbaijan State Political Department in 1924 [[Topchubashi & Rasulzadeh 2012, p. 26](#)], together with G. Salukvadze.

The defeat of the first underground

In the meantime, the United State Political Department closely monitored the formation of the Georgian-Azerbaijani anti-Soviet alliance. In June 1923, the first arrests of Musavatists were made. Some of them were soon released on condition that they would urge their comrades-in-arms to stop anti-Soviet activities. According to a leaflet issued by Mirzabala Mammadzadeh, not only members of the underground, but also representatives of the Azerbaijani intelligentsia who had nothing to do with them were arrested. They were all forced to declare themselves former members of Musavat, declare the activity of the underground ceased, and defect to the Bolsheviks. Mammadzadeh strongly condemned this violence and stated that in fact Musavatists remained loyal to their cause and were not going to defect to the Soviet government.

All the members of the Musavat Central Committee were subjected to repression. Abdul Vahhab Mamedzadeh, Rahim Vakilov, Karbalai Vali Mikayilov and others were arrested. Mirzabala Mammadzadeh tried to intensify the activities of the Musavat underground at that time, but the Azerbaijani State Political Department conducted more mass arrests of Musavat activists and put an end to the activities of the printing house he headed. Mamedzadeh fled abroad, but before that he informed Dadash Hasanov and Ahmad Hajinski that by the decision of the Central Committee they should lead and organize the further work of the party [[Final Decree 1926, p. 33](#)].

The defeat of the Azerbaijani underground was a serious blow to the planned general Caucasian uprising. In fact, the Azerbaijani State Political Department put an end to the existence of the active center of Musavatists and destroyed all their structures. A blow was also inflicted on the Georgian underground, and in August-September 1924 the Georgian insurrection failed and was crushed by the Red Army.

Illustration 2. Leaders of the second underground of the "Musavat" Party in Azerbaijan Prison Main Political Department: No. 4 - Chairman of the Central Committee Dadash Hasanov, No. 1 - Secretary of the Central Committee Ahmed Hajinsky.

Source: From the Hasanzadeh family album. Published with their permission.

II. THE MUSAVAT UNDERGROUND IN 1923-1926

Restoration of the underground

Some time after the defeat of the first Musavat underground, the activists, who escaped reprisals, continued their activities and began work to revive the party's activity [[Topchubashi & Rasulzadeh 2012, p. 48](#)].

The first meeting of activists of the second underground was held at Dadash Hasanov's apartment in November 1923. The meeting set up an interim committee with the rights of the Central Committee consisting of Hasanov, Hajinski, Abulfaz Babayev, Abdul Abdulzadeh and Ali Yusifzadeh. However,

later Abdulzadeh stopped taking part in the activities of the party and therefore was removed from the leadership, while Babayev was soon arrested. Therefore, only three members remained in the Central Committee. The chairman of the second Central Committee of the Party was Dr. Dadash Hasanov (1897-1927) [[Final Decree 1926, p. 70](#)], and the secretary was Ahmad Hajinski [[Zeynalov](#)].

The new composition of the Central Committee of the party confirmed its commitment to the policy of restoring Azerbaijan's state independence. However, the Musavatists stopped participating in the preparation of the general Caucasian uprising. Apparently this was due not only to their limited potential, but also to the revision of the party's policy. Specifically, while in emigration in November 1924, Mammad Amin Rasulzadeh opposed the insurrection, arguing that "as long as Russia is not involved in any serious war or as long as there are no serious complications in Russia, no armed uprising will have an effect, and we risk exposing our peoples to an unheard-of catastrophe that could delay the cause of liberation for many years" [[Topchubashi & Rasulzadeh 2012, p. 53](#)].

Until the end of 1924, all work was limited to finding funds for material assistance to the families of repressed Musavatists [[Topchubashi & Rasulzadeh 2012, p. 69](#)]. This was done mostly with the help of monthly membership fees (in the amount of 220-230 rubles per member).

From the beginning of 1925, the underground organization intensified its activities. In November, at a meeting in the apartment of Dadash Hasanov, a new composition of the Central Committee of the second underground was formed, which also included A. Hajinski, A. Babayev, M. G. Valiyev (Baharli) and R. Vakilov. A new composition of the BC was also elected, including Mir Abdul Gani Mir Gasimov, Gazanfar Sultanov (student of the Azerbaijan Pedagogical Institute), Suleyman Israfilov (student of the Azerbaijan Medical Institute), Habib Mammadov (teacher at the Narimanov Technical School).

The work of Musavatists in the counties also became more active. Specifically, a strong underground group was created in Karabakh. In the summer of 1925, even a plenum of the Karabakh branch of Musavat was held in Shusha, which was attended by Dadash Hasanov [[Guliyev 2001, p. 148](#)].

The chairman of the Central Committee, Dadash Hasanov, preferred to work with people who had been checked and refused to accept new members. In his directive, which he sent to the counties, he ordered members of the party to purge their ranks and remove indifferent, unprincipled and inactive people from their ranks, collect money to help repressed Musavatists, and engage in educational work [[Final Decree 1926, p. 43](#)]. He also said that violent clashes with the Soviet authorities are impossible as this will lead to senseless victims among the population. According to D. Hasanov, it is necessary to counter the activities of

other groups, especially the "İttihadists", who can organize such provocations.

Hasanov also believed that it was necessary to win over not only non-partisan citizens and supporters of Azerbaijan's independence, but also Communists, among whom Musavatists [[Zeynalov](#)] were conducting active propaganda. The investigative case mentions the names of enlisted members of the ACP (b) Suleyman Hajiyev and Seyid Rzayev. In addition, the Musavatists were ordered to disguise themselves and join the ACP (b) to undermine the Communist Party from within. For example, the ACP (b) in 1925 was joined by the Agdam Musavatists, Asad Nasirov and Movsum Ibrahimov, who were connected with Hasanov [Concluding Resolution 1926, p. 44]. One of the leaders of the second underground, Ahmad Hajinski, not being a member of the ACP (b), was nevertheless an editor of the Turkic department of Kommunist newspaper.

Educational activities

In the work of the second underground, significant prominence was given to the patriotic education of the Azerbaijani people and to the promotion of history and national values [[Amrahov 2009, p. 197](#)]. This was apparently facilitated by the directives of Mammad Amin Rasulzadeh, who insisted on active work in educating the population and strengthening the ideas of independence and Turkic unity in the people's self-consciousness [[Balaev 2013, p. 34](#)].

According to Dadash Hasanov, the goals must be achieved by "creating a corps of educated personnel that need to be introduced into the state and educational structures of Soviet institutions; as the number increases, the whole apparatus of power must be in the hands of supporters of independence" [[Final Decree 1926, p. 43](#)].

By November 1925, Ahmed Hajinski had drawn up a work plan entitled "Instruction on the non-party education of youth", which was planned to be implemented in educational institutions and educational circles [[Final Decree 1926, p. 47-49](#)]. According to this plan, it is necessary to instill a sense of love for the idea of Turkic unity and a sense of pride for belonging to the Turkic nation in young people. At the same time, young people must resist the occupation and attempts to Russify Turks. It is necessary to oppose only religious prejudices, but not the traditions and religion of our people. Children need to get initial knowledge about the history of Azerbaijan, and it is necessary to emphasize the occupation of the country by Bolshevik Russia. It is also necessary to study the history of Turkey and other Turkic regions in detail. Particular attention should be paid to classes in literature and to the teaching of works of Turkic authors, including Central Asian, Tatar and Turkish authors banned by the Soviet authorities. In geography classes, it is necessary to talk in more detail about the Turkic countries and regions and give detailed information about the countries that managed to get away from Russia's influence. Teachers should also carefully disclose knowledge of these disciplines

within the framework of the official policy approved by the Soviet authorities for educational institutions.

The enlightenment program of the Musavat party underground led to the creation of numerous patriotic youth organizations and circles in 1925-1931, which also operated in the educational institutions of Azerbaijan [[Yagublu 2012, p. 136](#)]. As a result of the work of the Musavat underground, a growth in nationalistic sentiments among young people was recorded. According to the materials of the investigative case, as early as 1925, "a youth organization of the Turkic people" was established in School No. 18 and at the Pedagogical Technical School and worked against the Komsomol cells of these educational institutions on whose walls their leaflets were posted" [[Final Decree 1926, p. 50](#)]. The content of the leaflets contained a protest against the dominance of the Russian language in Azerbaijan and the restriction on a decent education in the Turkic language.

Work was also carried out to spread nationalist literature banned by the Soviet authorities. In particular, two leaflets were printed, and books by M. A. Rasulzadeh "Azərbaycanın keçmişi və gələcəyi" (the past and future of Azerbaijan) and "Türkçülüyn əsasları" (Fundamentals of Turkism), as well as several issues of Yeni Qafqasiya journal (New Caucasus), which he published in Turkey, were distributed.

Significant prominence in the secret meetings of that period was given to the Turkic Congress, which was scheduled to be held in Baku in 1926. It was decided to support this event, but to abandon the idea of changing the alphabet from Arabic to Latin [[Yagublu 2012, p. 134](#)]. The leaflet issued by members of the Central Committee on this problem said that there was a need to change the alphabet. However, this issue is being promoted by the Bolsheviks for their political purposes in order to split the Turkic world and not to allow it to be integrated. A new unified alphabet should be adopted not only for Azerbaijan, but also for all Turkic peoples. But this is what the Bolsheviks do not want to allow. Therefore, at present it is necessary to oppose the change of the alphabet and to solve this issue in the future in the interests of all Turkic peoples [[Final Decree 1926, p. 45-46](#)].

Relations with emigration

According to the materials of the investigative case, at the end of 1925, in Dadash Hasanov's apartment, Memduh Sevket bey handed the Musavatists a letter from Rasulzadeh in which he asked why members of the underground in Baku did not contact him and did not inform him about the situation in Azerbaijan. In the same letter, he wrote that the international situation continues to remain uncertain, but nevertheless one cannot lose hope for the restoration of Azerbaijan's independence.

Then, Rasulzadeh warned that a certain group, having received a large sum of

money from foreign forces, is going to stage a provocation on the border between Iran and Azerbaijan and asked to send Musavatists there to stop their provocations, because many people may die as a result of it.

Rasulzadeh also sent books and several editions of Yeni Qafqasiya journal. He asked them to sell them, send the cost price to him in Turkey and hand over the profit to both his family members and the families of repressed Musavatists. Unable to reunite with his family, Rasulzadeh regularly sent them help until the tightening of the border rules in 1929 [[Balaev 2013, p. 51](#)].

Mirzabala Mammadzadeh also gave members of the underground various literature from Iran, including editions of Yeni Qafqasiya journal, which had been sent there from Turkey [[Mamulia & Abutalybov 2014, p. 253](#)].

According to the investigation materials, Azerbaijani emigration and Rasulzadeh received military information through the Turkish mission in Baku. At the end of 1925, Dadash Hasanov issued a special directive: "In counties, it is necessary to gather information about the number of servicemen, police and their commanders. It is also necessary to find out whether they have guns and machine guns, and how many. It is also necessary to pay special attention to entities that use the railway and have our own people there" [[Final Decree 1926, p. 56](#)].

The defeat of the second underground

According to the materials of the investigative case headed by Mir Jafar Bagirov, the future secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party (Bolsheviks), "the Azerbaijani State Political Department became aware that there was a clearly defined center of the Musavat party that operated throughout Azerbaijan and had connections with the Musavat emigration" [[Final Decree 1926, p. 1](#)]. Thus, on March 11, 1926, the leaders of the second underground, Dadash Hasanov, Ahmed Hajinski and Ali Yusifzadeh, were arrested. After that, mass repressions against Musavatists took place throughout Azerbaijan.

After the arrest of Hasanov, the underground was led by Abulfaz Babayev, who was arrested in July 1926. After his arrest, only Baharli and Vakilov among members of the Central Committee remained free, and in spite of the most severe repressions, they did not stop their activities and formed the new leadership of the BC consisting of Mir Abdul Gani Mir Gasimov, Gazanfar Sultanov, Suleyman Israfilov and Habib Mammadov. Thus, the activists of the underground tried not to allow the activity of Musavatists to cease in Azerbaijan. However, a little later, they were all arrested too.

The liquidation of the underground continued until October 1926. In all, 34

people were arrested. They were accused of restoring the first Musavat underground, which was liquidated in 1923, and its military organization, of espionage and intelligence gathering in favor of foreign intelligence services, attempts to destroy the ACP (B) and government bodies from within and preparing to seize power in Azerbaijan.

According to the sentence handed down by the court session of the board of the United State Political Department on February 28, 1927, Dadash Hasanov, Movsum Ibrahimov, Javad Akhundov and Mir Bagir Seyid Rzayev were sentenced to death. The remaining members of the underground were sentenced to six to ten years and sent to the Butyrskaya prison in Moscow. The sentence was enforced on April 6, 1927.

After the defeat of the second underground, it was not possible to revive the strong organized center of the Musavat party. However, individual cells of members of the underground continued their activities for many years and were subjected to reprisals by the special services of the USSR.

CONCLUSIONS

Despite the fact that immediately after the occupation of Azerbaijan by Soviet Russia, a resistance movement began, nevertheless, it was largely unorganized and spontaneous. The organization of clandestine activities by the members of the Musavat Party who remained in the country and did not emigrate abroad was an attempt to create such an organizational center that could lead protest moods.

At the same time, it should be noted that the Musavat Party, which ruled Azerbaijan in 1918-1920 and led the country to independence, considerably changed after the Soviet occupation and actually became a leftist nationalist party. Musavatists of the underground set up an organization with new goals and tasks, which amounted to the restoration of the state independence of Azerbaijan.

The underground managed to create an organizational structure with clear programs and goals and declare itself as a serious political force on which the entire punitive apparatus of the Soviet authorities cracked down.

The activists of the second Musavat underground managed to influence the further education of the Azerbaijani people. Thanks to their efforts, a network of various enlightening and patriotic circles was formed in which young people were educated, the creative abilities of the Azerbaijani intelligentsia were realized, and the national self-consciousness of the people grew. The results of this activity affected the general moods of the Azerbaijani intelligentsia and the policy of the leadership of Azerbaijan in the post-Stalin era. This process could not be stopped even by the most severe repression in the late 1930s.

Eventually, a few decades after those events, the goal set by the fighters for the independence of Azerbaijan was achieved and the country gained independence. The selfless ideological struggle of the underground and the numerous sacrifices that the Azerbaijani people suffered in the struggle for independence were not in vain. The ideas of independence, for which members of the Azerbaijani underground fought, were realized on August 30, 1991, when the Supreme Council of Azerbaijan adopted the declaration "On the Restoration of the State Independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan". Over the years of independence, despite the hard trials, the country strengthened, developed and proved its viability.

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